

UNRAVELLING THE EFFECT OF THE ADDITION OF A NEW CARBON ALLOTROPE IN POLYMERIC COMPOSITES: INVESTIGATION OF ELECTRICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

The discovery of new carbon allotropes has led to major advancements in materials science, as each new form of carbon has unique properties that can lead to new applications. The variety of structures and characteristics existing in carbon allotropes provides unprecedented mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties. However, even though these new forms are revolutionary, their synthesis process is difficult. The production processes are complex and often need extreme conditions or highly specialized production techniques, which make their production and application challenging.

A recent milestone in this field has been the identification of the hexagonal carbon allotrope RH6-II developed through a novel morphing mechanism in graphene nanostructures, which represents a significant shift from traditional sp²-bonded carbon structures, introducing a hybrid bonding configuration of sp² and sp³ carbons. This new structure showed unique atomic arrangements that differentiate it from conventional graphene or diamond structures. In this work, we build upon these findings by investigating the effect of the incorporation of RH6-II allotrope within polymeric composites. Given the increasing electrical conductivity with RH6-II content, these nanostructures hold potential for applications in structural composites, where both mechanical reinforcement and enhanced electrical properties are desirable. Future improvements in RH6-II production yield could further facilitate its use in various composite applications.

1 INTRODUCTION

The research for innovative carbon-based reinforcements for structural and functional purposes is one of the most advanced frontiers of materials science. During the past half century, the discovery of fullerenes [1], carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [2] and graphene related materials [3] has dramatically changed the world of research. Nevertheless, the carbon family has recently grown by adding a new carbon allotrope named morphed graphene [4-6]. Morphed graphene, shown in Figure 1, is composed of

distorted covalently cross-linked graphene layers bonded with a sp^2 hybridization but a sp^3 -like arrangement. Among its phases, morphed graphene RH6-II phase is a rippled structure emerging when graphene sheets undergo mechanical deformation induced by compressive strain promoted by ball milling [4]. RH6-II phase is formed as a result of energy minimization under strain when the pristine graphene buckles rather than stretches further or tear. This structural change decreases the overall elastic energy of the system leading to a stable, non-planar configuration. Though the atomic connectivity of graphene remains intact, the out-of-plane deformation significantly alters its physical properties. Electronically, the RH6-II morphology can induce changes in the band structure of graphene. Local curvature generates strain fields that open small bandgaps or produce pseudomagnetic effects, which are absent in pristine graphene.

Figure 1: Mechanical synthesis of morphed graphene. Reprinted with permission.

Morphed graphene is characterized by astonishing properties as mechanical reinforcement agent in a wide range of matrices in concentrations ranging from 1 wt% up to 5 wt.% [7-10] showing mechanical properties improvements of up to 2 orders of magnitude with an increase of 73%, 25% and 250% in elastic energy ratio, hardness and toughness [7-11]. On the other hand, morphed graphene electrical properties are not well described and actually neglected in the composite science. Accordingly, this work will investigate the electrical properties of morphed graphene containing polymeric composites in both DC and AC regimes also considering how the surface properties are changing in a wide range of filler concentration.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. MATERIALS

The morphed graphene was manufactured using PetCoke a very abundant oil-and-gas soot byproduct. The PetCoke was ground in a Nutribullet® for periods of 1 minute at a time until fine powder (-150 mesh) was produced. The fines are collected and milled for periods of 1 h to 10 h in a Spex mill. The final product is morphed graphene (MG). The Spex procedure was previously reported in [4, 5, 12].

Poly(vinylbutyral)(PVB) was purchased by Sigma Aldrich and used without any further purification.

Composites were prepared by mechanically mixing morphed graphene with PVB in acetone and cast into molds until the solvent was evaporated.

2.2 CHARACTERIZATIONS

Raman spectroscopy was performed using a Renishaw inVia spectrometer (H43662 model, Gloucestershire, UK) equipped with 514 nm laser line with a 100× objective. Raman spectrum was recorded in the range from 250 cm^{-1} to 4000 cm^{-1} . Raman spectrum was fitted by using the methodology proposed by Tagliaferro et al. [13].

Morphed graphene morphology was studied by using a field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM, Zeis SupraTM40, Oberkochen, Germany) equipped with an energy dispersive X-ray detector (EDX, Oxford Inca Energy 450, Oberkochen, Germany).

XRD analysis were run on a powder sample using aPanalytical X'PERT PRO PW3040/60 diffractometer, with Cu K radiation at 40 kV and 40 mA, Panalytical BV, Almelo in the 2θ range from 10 to 80 °with a step size of 0.013 °.

The wetting properties were investigated by optical contact angle (OCA) measurements with the sessile drop technique, using an OCAH 200 (DataPhysic Instruments). Two different liquid probes were used: water (H₂O) and diiodomethane (CH₂I₂). Each liquid drop (1 μL in volume) was dispensed, and the image of the drop on the sample was acquired with the integrated high-resolution camera. The drop profiles were extracted and fitted with dedicated software (SCA20) using the Young-Laplace method, and contact angles at the liquid-solid interface between fitted function and baseline were calculated. For each sample and each liquid probe, the contact angle measurement was repeated three times on different areas. The polar and dispersive components of the surface energy were evaluated by applying the Owens-Wendt method [14].

The DC electrical conductivity of the composites was measured at room temperature (295 K) by electrically contacting the composite samples in the four-point van der Pauw configuration by using thin gold wires and conducting silver paste (RS Components, Sesto San Giovanni, Italy). The resistance of each van der Pauw configuration was measured using the four-probe resistance option of a 34410 multimeter (Keysight Technologies, Santa Rosa, CA, USA). The conductivity was then calculated as $\sigma = R_s^{-1}t^{-1}$, where R_s is the sheet resistance obtained by solving the van der Pauw equation, and t is the thickness of the material.

The complex permittivity of the samples was measured in the GHz range by means of a cylindrical coaxial cell (EpsiMu toolkit [15]), containing the sample as a spacer between inner and outer conductors, whose diameters are 0.6 cm and 1.3 cm, respectively. Two conical parts link the cell to standard connectors, allowing it to keep the characteristic impedance to 50 W, thus avoiding mismatch and energy loss. The cell is connected to a ZVK Vector Network Analyzer (Rohde & Schwarz GmbH, Munich, Germany), suitably calibrated, and measurements are analyzed with a two-port transmission line technique. The electromagnetic properties of the sample are determined by de-embedding and the Nicolson-Ross-Weir transmission/reflection algorithm [16, 17].

3 RESULTS

3.1 Physico-chemical properties of MG and related composites

Morphed Graphene was analyzed using Raman spectroscopy in the range from 250 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹ as reported in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Raman spectra of morphed graphene in the range from 250 cm⁻¹ to 4000 cm⁻¹ fitted accordingly with the procedure reported by Tagliaferro et al.[13]

As shown in Figure 2, the D and G peaks are represented by a component (named D) centered at 1343 cm⁻¹ and two components named G¹ and G² centered at 1480 cm⁻¹ and 1580 cm⁻¹ respectively [18]

while the 2D region is composed by three components known as 2D, D+G, 2D centered at 2687, 2915 and 3163 cm^{-1} respectively. According to Shimoidara et al. [19], the G^2 peak is originated from graphitic domains characterized by a high order of bond angle while G^1 arises from amorphous domains with greater disorder. The ration between G^1 and G^2 can be used for the evaluation of bond angle disorder and morphed graphene is characterized by a value of 0.41 inferior that is considerably lower than non-activated carbon black that is close to 0.6 [19]. This suggest that the milling process promotes a greater angular order, as also evidenced by the ID/IG ratio of 0.97. Such a value suggests the presence of a long-range structural order, comparable to that observed in non-graphitizable carbon treated at high temperatures [20-29]. Moreover, the calculated volumetric crystallite size L_a is 17.2 nm [30]. It is also noticed the presence of a peak centered at 863 cm^{-1} (marked with a star) due to iron oxide trace or organic-rich residue from the original pet coke [31].

Morphed Graphene was analyzed using XRD spectroscopy in the range from 10° to 80° as reported in Figure 3.

Figure 3: XRD spectra of morphed graphene between 10° to 80° .

XRD spectra show three large components centered at 19.1° , 24.7° and 44.1° respectively as reported by Calderon et al. [4] due to different lattice modes. Using the component at 24.7° (basal lattice mode), RH6-IIa phase with a crystallite size of 1.52 ± 0.29 nm calculated using Scherrer equation [32] in agreement with TEM data reporter by Calderon et al. [4].

The morphological analysis reported in Figure 4 showed the presence of round shaped particles with an average size of 41 ± 6 nm and a carbon content of up to 90.2 wt.% and an oxygen amount of 9.8.

Figure 4: Morphological and elemental analysis of RH6-II.

For both atmosphere (air and argon, see Figure 5) the TGA of morphed graphene have a weight loss between 25 and 100 °C due to the moisture of the sample. In air atmosphere there is a significant weight loss starting around 350 °C, with a rapid decomposition occurring up to approximately 550 °C, after which the weight stabilizes, indicating complete degradation of the combustible components. This sharp weight loss suggests oxidative degradation. In contrast, under an argon atmosphere, the weight loss is more gradual and continues over the entire temperature range. This indicates that in the absence of oxygen, the material decomposes more slowly, likely through pyrolysis rather than combustion. Overall, the data highlights the strong influence of the atmospheric environment on the thermal degradation behavior of the material.

Figure 5: Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of morphed graphene in argon and air condition.

As shown in Figure 6, the superficial energy of the composite system, determined from contact angle measurements showed a two-regime behavior as a function of RH6-II content. In the low concentration range up to 40 wt.%, the superficial energy remains almost constant at 40 mN/m, indicating that the addition of RH6-II does not significantly alter the wettability of the composite surface. This suggests that RH6-II particles were either well embedded within the PVB matrix or did not form a continuous

surface layer that modifies the overall surface chemistry. Above a threshold concentration of 50 wt.%), a sharp increment in superficial energy was observed together with a strong linear dependence on RH6-II content ($R^2 \approx 0.98$). This drastic change supported a percolation-like behavior where RH6-II particles begin to dominate the surface properties. The structure of RH6-II, characterized by a hierarchical arrangement of conductive domains and amorphous regions, plays a crucial role in this transition. At low concentrations, the polymer matrix drives the surface properties whereas at high concentrations, RH6-II's intrinsic surface chemistry, including its potential oxygen-containing functional groups and rough morphology, enhance the surface energy.

Figure 6: Contact angle measurement of RH6-II loaded PVB composites.

As shown in Figure 7, the DC electrical conductivity measurements revealed clear percolative behavior in the PVB-based composites containing RH6-II as a conductive filler. For RH6-II loadings lower than 10 wt.%, no measurable conductivity values were obtained, and therefore these points are not reported in the figure. This suggests that at such low filler content, the RH6-II particles remain too isolated to establish conductive paths, and the composite maintains an insulating behavior similar to that of neat PVB ($1 \times 10^{-13} \text{ S m}^{-1}$ {Roy, 2014 #500}) due to the too dispersed filler particles being unable to form percolating conductive pathways. A dramatic increase in DC conductivity by nearly 10 orders of magnitude ($6.6 \pm 2.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S m}^{-1}$) was observed at a RH6-II loading of 10%, which indicates the successful establishment of a percolative conductive network across the sample. Increasing the filler content up to a RH6-II loading of 50% results in a further increment of the DC conductivity by another order of magnitude (up to a value of $8.9 \pm 0.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ S m}^{-1}$) with no sign of saturation. Indeed, the inset to Figure 6 shows that the experimental conductivity values as a function of the filler concentration are in fair agreement with the expected behavior for a percolative network

$$\sigma \propto (x - x_c)^\beta$$

where σ is the DC conductivity, x is the concentration of conductive particles, x_c is the critical concentration for percolation, and β is the percolation exponent. The fit to our experimental data gives $\beta \approx 1.5$, as expected for a standard three-dimensional network {Kirkpatrick, 1973 #501} and indicates that the improvement in conductivity can be largely ascribed to an increment in the percolation probability in the entire RH-II loading range. As the filler content exceeds 50 wt.%, conductivity may approach saturation, resembling the behavior of a conductive network with an insulating phase dispersed within it. Compared to other conductive fillers, RH6-II provides distinct advantages: whereas graphene offers high conductivity, its dispersion in polymer matrices is challenging, and sedimentation can disrupt electrical continuity. Carbon black, on the other hand, consists of nanometric spherical particles with lower intrinsic conductivity than RH6-II, requiring higher loadings to achieve percolation. The observed

percolative behavior in RH6-II-based composites confirms its potential as an effective conductive filler, with possible applications in electromagnetic shielding, EMI attenuation, and flexible electronics.

Figure 7: DC electrical conductivity of RH6-II loaded PVB composites in ambient conditions (filled circles) and literature value for neat PVB (hollow circle) {Roy, 2014 #500}. Inset shows the same data in bilogarithmic scale (filled circles) with the fit to standard percolation theory (dashed line).

3.2 Modelling of shielding properties of MG containing composites

The electromagnetic shielding properties in the GHz frequency range can be modelled starting from the microwave characterization, in terms of the complex permittivity $\epsilon = \epsilon' - j\epsilon''$. The real part of the permittivity for the reference PVB is shown as a function of frequency in the lower panel of Figure 8, while its increments $\Delta\epsilon'$ in composites with different RH6-II contents – with respect to the neat material – are shown in the upper panel.

Figure 8: Real part of the complex permittivity for the reference PVB sample (lower panel) and its increments in composites with different RH6-II contents (upper panel).

The AC conductivity σ is related to the imaginary part of the permittivity by $\varepsilon'' = \sigma/\omega\varepsilon_0$. In Figure 9, the AC conductivity as a function of the RH6-II content, obtained at different frequencies, is compared to the DC conductivity already reported in Figure 7.

Figure 9: DC and AC conductivity for composites with different RH-II contents. Lines are guides to the eye.

Finally, the ratio of the imaginary to the real part of the complex permittivity gives the loss tangent, that can be used together with the conductivity in the formulae reported in Ref. 28 to calculate the overall electromagnetic shielding efficiency

$$SE = 10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{P_i}{P_t} \right)$$

as a sum of absorption, reflection, and multiple-reflection contributions (here, P_i and P_t are the incident power and the power transmitted through the shield, respectively). It turns out that the dominant term is the absorption one, and that a significant shielding efficiency can be obtained at frequencies above about 3 GHz (Figure 10).

Figure 10: shielding efficiency for a 10-mm-thick composite with RH6-II content of 50 wt.%, as a function of frequency.

4. CONCLUSIONS

In this study, we investigated the electrical properties of RH6-II in both AC and DC regimes by incorporating morphed graphene into a filmable polymeric matrix. The analysis of physicochemical properties allowed us to draw a complete picture of the exotic RH6-II supporting our further considerations based on solid structural insights. Electrical analysis highlighted a stable charge transport mechanism over the examined frequency domain with SE dominated by absorption mechanism. The evaluation on a 10 mm RH6-II based composite showed that SE increased significantly above 3 GHz supporting the utilization of these species for high-frequency electromagnetic interference in which multiple layers of the composites are added. Accordingly, these materials can be used in aerospace layered composites as engineered connection layers between structural ones or in advanced communication devices such as those operating using 5G technology and electronic components that demand robust EMI protection without requirements of thickness. Furthermore, the combination of mechanical flexibility and processability of these composites together with their SE properties can find application in smart devices for biomedical applications including in vivo sensors due also to the high surface energy that can prevent the proliferation of bacterial biofilm.

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